

THE EURO-GLOBAL PLATFORM FOR MECHANISM-BASED DRUG REPURPOSING

REPO4EU News – December 2024

Dear colleague,

Welcome to our end-of-year newsletter! As we wrap up an inspiring 2024, we are excited to share some key updates and upcoming milestones for 2025. The coming of a new year always signifies great challenges and even greater opportunities. As such, we will kick off 2025 with our first hybrid policy event in Brussels to echo our unwavering commitment to advocate for sustainable drug repurposing models. Also, following its official introduction this summer, our Drug Repurposing journal returns, again packed with expert insights, research, and interdisciplinary collaboration. And there's even more to look forward to, so mark next September in your calendar for the upcoming RExPO25 conference in Barcelona.

At REPO4EU, we look forward to welcoming you at these exciting events and continuing our shared journey toward innovation in drug repurposing. Stay engaged, stay disruptive!

Prof. Harald Schmidt
MD, PhD, PharmD
Coordinator of REPO4EU – Maastricht University

Exploring innovative and sustainable models for drug repurposing

New year, new beginnings! Next January 15, we will be hosting our first hybrid policy kick-off event in Brussels, where the REPO4EU consortium –with the support of the EU– will be putting forward a proposal for the creation of a Special Interest Group (SIG), with the ultimate goal of advocating for and streamlining innovative and sustainable models for repurposed drugs. Thus, we are honored to invite our community of clinicians, researchers, policymakers and corporate representatives to take part in this event and help us unlock the potential of drug repurposing. Follow the link to find out more and do not miss the opportunity to register and join us in this crucial conversation!

[Take a look and register now](#)

Our Drug Repurposing journal is back for its second issue

The Drug Repurposing journal –our diamond Open Access journal for the drug repurposing community– aims to provide an interdisciplinary and cross-sectional overview of the various fields of research and applied sciences that work together to make successful drug repurposing projects a reality. The inaugural edition of the journal was publicly launched back in July at our RExPO24 conference. It includes a collection of discussion articles, research papers, and reviews catalyzing progress and collaboration in drug repurposing, and inviting contributions from a wide array of focus areas: from bioinformatics and clinical trials, all the way to ethics and patenting strategies. Now, the journal is back for its second issue – click below to browse through all the key contents and expert insights we have collated for this latest edition!

[Learn more](#)

RexP025

THE 4TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON
SYSTEMS MEDICINE, AI & DRUG REPURPOSING

BARCELONA
SEPTEMBER 24-26 2025

Save the date for RExP025, the next installment in our conference series

The countdown is officially on for RExP025 –the fourth edition of our annual conference on Systems Medicine, AI & Drug Repurposing–, an event that brings together world-leading experts from across the entire pharma innovation ecosystem, including clinicians, researchers, SMEs, policymakers and patient representatives.

Next year's edition will be hosted in Barcelona on September 24-26, and will be co-hosted by REPO4EU's project coordinator Harald Schmidt and our colleague Lynn Durham, CEO and Founder at STALICLA. Registration will open very soon, and we will be covering a wide and exciting range of topics, from rare diseases, network medicine and precision diagnostics, all the way to drug reformulation, patient engagement and innovative trials. In the meantime, make sure to click the link below for the latest updates on RExP025, including key topics, logistics and the preliminary agenda.

[This is RExP025](#)

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